

THE BEST WAY TO IMPROVE READING AND WRITING SKILLS

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Annotation: The skills required for writing and reading are largely the same. Since spelling and single-word reading share the same foundational knowledge, training in one area should support the growth of the other. For example, when students read and write the same words, it strengthens their capacity to combine sounds to form words. Additionally, teaching writing skills and improving reading comprehension are two benefits of writing training. Studies indicate that the most effective way to develop reading and writing skills is to teach and practice them simultaneously. Researchers have shown that a crucial component in helping students increase their comprehension is instructional technique. Nevertheless, a lot of educators don't have a strong basis in teaching these reading comprehension techniques. As a result, educators must be knowledgeable about creating and imparting excellent comprehension techniques to their students. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate efficient reading techniques to enhance language learners' reading abilities. The study is an application of action research to a group of fourteen students enrolled in an intermediate level course on integrated skills. The study's central query is "Would reading strategies help my students' reading comprehension studies?" The study's findings show that the pupils significantly improved after receiving instruction in reading skills.

Аннотация: Навыки, необходимые для письма и чтения, во многом одинаковы. Поскольку правописание и чтение отдельных слов имеют одни и те же базовые знания, обучение в одной области должно способствовать развитию другой. Например, когда учащиеся читают и пишут одни и те же слова, это укрепляет их способность объединять звуки в слова. Кроме того, обучение навыкам письма и улучшение понимания прочитанного являются двумя преимуществами обучения письму. Исследования показывают, что наиболее эффективный способ развития навыков чтения и письма — это одновременное их обучение и практика. Исследователи показали, что важнейшим компонентом помощи учащимся в улучшении понимания является техника обучения. Тем не менее, многие преподаватели не имеют прочной основы для обучения этим методам понимания прочитанного. В результате преподаватели должны быть осведомлены о создании и передаче превосходных методов понимания своим ученикам. Таким образом, целью данного исследования является изучение

эффективных методов чтения для улучшения навыков чтения у изучающих язык. Исследование представляет собой приложение практического исследования к группе из четырнадцати студентов, обучающихся на курсе интегрированных навыков среднего уровня. Главный вопрос исследования: «Помогут ли стратегии чтения моим ученикам в изучении понимания прочитанного?» Результаты исследования показывают, что ученики значительно улучшились после обучения навыкам чтения.

Anotatsiya: Yozish va o'qish uchun talab qilinadigan ko'nikmalar asosan bir xil. Imlo va bir so'zli o'qish bir xil asosiy bilimlarga ega bo'lganligi sababli, bir sohada o'qitish boshqa sohaning o'sishiga yordam berishi kerak. Masalan, o'quvchilar bir xil so'zlarni o'qish va yozishda tovushlarni birlashtirib so'z hosil qilish qobiliyatini kuchaytiradi. Bundan tashqari, yozish ko'nikmalarini o'rgatish va o'qishni tushunishni yaxshilash yozishni o'rgatishning ikkita foydasidir. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'qish va yozish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning eng samarali usuli ularni bir vaqtning o'zida o'rgatish va mashq qilishdir. Tadqiqotchilar shuni ko'rsatdiki, o'quvchilarning tushunish qobiliyatini oshirishga yordam beradigan muhim komponent bu o'qitish texnikasi. Shunga qaramay, ko'plab o'qituvchilar ushbu o'qishni tushunish usullarini o'rgatishda mustahkam asosga ega emaslar. Natijada, o'qituvchilar o'z talabalariga mukammal tushunish usullarini yaratish va berish haqida bilimga ega bo'lishlari kerak. Shu sababli, ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi til o'rganuvchilarning o'qish qobiliyatini oshirish uchun samarali o'qish usullarini o'rganishdir. Tadqiqot integratsiyalashgan ko'nikmalar bo'yicha o'rta darajadagi kursda o'qiyotgan o'n to'rt nafar talabalar guruhiga harakat tadqiqotini qo'llashdir. Tadqiqotning markaziy so'rovi "O'qish strategiyalari o'quvchilarim o'qishni tushunishga yordam beradimi?" Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'quvchilar o'qish qobiliyatlari bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar olgandan keyin sezilarli darajada yaxshilangan.

Keywords: literacy abilities, practice, constitutes, feedback, outline, brainstorming, intimidating,

Ключевые слова: способности к грамотности, практика, составляет, обратная связь, схема, мозговой штурм, запугивание.

Kalit so'zlar: savodxonlik qobiliyatlari, Amaliyot, tashkil etadi, fikr-mulohaza, kontur, Aqliy hujum, qo'rqitish.

INTRODUCTION

Proficiency in reading enables an individual to communicate and comprehend written language. To independently understand the intended meaning being sent in the written content, one needs grasp a number of components. The first is phonemic awareness, which is described as "recognizing and manipulating spoken words in language" by the National Reading Panel. The same group defines oral reading fluency

as "reading text with speed, accuracy, and expression" and phonics as "understanding letter-sound correspondences in reading and spelling." Finally, comprehension is described as "directly teaching students to be aware of the cognitive processes involved in reading." Vocabulary is the fourth component and is defined as "understanding words read by linking the word to oral vocabulary." The ability to read, understand, interpret, and decode written language and texts is referred to as reading skills. The ability to comprehend and react to written communications, such as emails, messages, letters, and other written communications, can be greatly aided by exceptional reading skills. It's crucial to use reading comprehension abilities at work to ensure clear written communication, which can reduce misunderstandings and miscommunication. In addition, reading skills can include a number of essential elements that contribute to the development of general literacy abilities, such as vocabulary, comprehension, fluency, and techniques for helping readers decipher and understand texts. Writing abilities are what you need to write clearly and concisely. A competent writer is one who can make their argument to the reader in a clear and understandable manner, without resorting to excessive filler. The act of writing itself is only one aspect of writing talents. Important steps in the writing process include conducting research, organizing, planning and outlining, editing, and revising, as well as using proper language and spelling. Writing skills involve adequate knowledge and the ability to express your thoughts and ideas in written words. It refers to a sound understanding of language through grammar, punctuation marks, and spelling. A good writing skill also includes writing style and tone of the language etc. Good writing skills allow the communicator to communicate his message so clearly to the targeted audience and make them understand easily. But remember one thing effective writing is not a simple task. It demands a detailed knowledge of sentence structure, grammar, vocabulary power, punctuation marks, exclamation marks and some basic writing skills. However, can be improved through consistent practice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is possible to strengthen your reading skills in a number of ways. Make notes each time you encounter unfamiliar vocabulary or practice speed reading to improve your fluency. Listed below are 7 strategies you can use to improve your reading skills:

1. Summarize what you read

Reading skills can be improved by summarizing what you read. Taking notes in your own words and from your own unique perspective forces you to remember specific details and central topics about what you read. To retain and comprehend what you read, you might want to share information with a friend or write a short summary.

2. While reading, take notes.

Taking notes while reading is another highly effective method for strengthening your reading skills. You might take notes while reading a fiction novel to gain a more

profound understanding of the author’s language choices, or you might write down new vocabulary while reading a science journal. You can ask questions about what you read and make connections when you take notes effectively. Likewise, charts, tables, and diagrams can clarify themes and ideas and help you draw inferences from your reading. As well as comprehension exercises like summarizing, note-taking can be highly beneficial.

3. Use key reading strategies

You can increase your comprehension by applying several key strategies as you read different texts. If you preview a text, you may identify its structure as informative, persuasive, or instructional. You might also identify key features of different texts, such as the central themes, problems, and solutions, or comparative ideas. You can improve your reading skills by identifying text features, determining the purpose, and taking notes.

4. The purpose should be determined

Practice determining the purpose of different texts as you read them. Take a moment to consider why different texts were written and what meanings or themes can be derived from them. Additionally, you might identify the purpose of reading, such as finding information, following instructions in a manual, or enjoying a story. When you know why you are reading a text, you can look for key ideas and details that support that purpose.

5. Read the texts in advance

Another way to strengthen your reading skills is to preview and scan texts. Using this strategy, you can preview titles, captions, headlines, and other text features to get an idea of what you will read. This can help you formulate the fundamental ideas that are behind a text before diving into the full piece.

6. Goals should be set for reading

It is possible to set reading goals for yourself in order to develop a wider vocabulary, gain a more in-depth understanding of different texts, and improve your ability to connect what you read with your own perspectives. If you are interested in business management, technology, or another subject that interests you, you might set a goal to learn different vocabulary related to that subject. As you read, you can discover meanings for unfamiliar words that help you build your vocabulary. Your vocabulary will grow as you become familiar with higher-level words and phrases.

7. Every day, make time to read

Finally, read every day. Lisa Cron’s “Wired for Story” is a compelling read that uses brain science to demonstrate how our minds are “wired” to respond to stories, providing a unique blend of neurological research and literary technique to help engage and understand stories better.

Writing is frequently a daily chore in numerous occupations spanning diverse industries, from sending emails to creating presentations. Writing abilities extend beyond spelling and grammar. Making sure your writing is communicating the intended message involves a number of factors, including accuracy, clarity, persuasiveness, and several more. Writing, like any other skill, is something we can get better at with time and practice. Here are some strategies for developing your own written communication:

Review grammar and spelling basics.

Grammar and spelling form the foundation of good writing. Writing with proper grammar and spelling communicates your professionalism and attention to detail to your reader. It also makes your writing easier to understand. Plus, knowing when and how to use less-common punctuation, like colons, semicolons, and em-dashes, can unlock new ways to structure sentences and elevate your writing. If you’re looking to strengthen your grammar and spelling, start by consulting a writing manual. *The Elements of Style* by William Strunk and E.B. White has long been considered a staple for writers. You can find similar resources at your local library, bookstore, or online.

Go over your intended writing. Understanding what constitutes a polished work of writing will help you with your own. Learn to write amusing short tales by reading those that are humorous. Composing a critique on a book? Look for a handful, and observe their structures. Take note of their strengths and the qualities you wish to imitate (without copying, of course). If you're writing on an assignment for class, you can ask your teacher for samples of previous students' well-written work. To get better at writing, incorporate reading into your daily routine. Prior to going to bed, consider reading a book or the news in the morning. If you've never read much, make a commitment to do so now.

3. Proofread.

While it’s tempting to submit work as soon as you’re done with it, build in some time to revisit what you’ve written to catch errors big and small. Here are a few proofreading tips to keep in mind:

- **Set your work aside before you edit.** Try to step away from your writing for a day or more so you can come back to it with fresh, more objective eyes. Crunched for time? Even allotting 20 minutes between writing and proofreading can allow you to approach your work with renewed energy.

- **Start with easy fixes, then progress to bigger changes.** Starting with easier changes can get you in the rhythm for proofreading, allow you to read through your work once more, and clear distractions so you can focus on bigger edits. Read through your work to catch misspellings, inconsistencies, and grammar errors. Then address the larger problems with structure or awkward transitions.

• **If you could say something in fewer words, do so.** Being unnecessarily wordy can cloud your message and confuse the reader. Pare down phrases that are redundant, repetitive, or obvious.

• **Read out loud.** Reading out loud can help you find awkward phrases and areas where your writing doesn’t flow well.

4. Get feedback.

Whether you’re writing emails or essays, asking for feedback is a great way to see how somebody besides yourself will interpret your text. Have an idea of what you’d like your proofreader to focus on—the structure, conclusion, the persuasiveness of an argument, or otherwise.

Approach a trusted friend, family member, coworker, or instructor. If you’re a student, your school might also have a writing resource center you can reach out to.

You might also consider forming a writing group or joining a writing class. Find writing courses online, at your local community college, or at independent writing workshops in your city.

5. Think about structure.

Grammar and spelling keep your writing consistent and legible, but structure ensures the big ideas get across to the reader.

In many cases, forming an **outline** will help solidify structure. An outline can clarify what you’re hoping to convey in each section, enable you to visualize the flow of your piece, and surface parts that require more research or thought.

Structure might look different depending on what you’re writing. An essay typically has an introduction, body paragraphs, and a conclusion. A fiction piece might follow the six-stage plot structure: exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, resolution, and denouement. Choose what’s best for your purposes.

6. Write.

Like many skills, one of the best ways to improve your writing is to practice. Here are a few ways you can get started:

- Start a journal or a blog.
- Join a class or writing workshop.
- Practice free writing.
- Write letters to friends or family.

7. Know some common fixes.

Even if a text is grammatically correct, you may be able to make it more dynamic and interesting with some polish. Here are some common ways you can sharpen your writing:

- Choose strong verbs (for example, “sprinted,” “dashed,” or “bolted” instead of “ran”).
- Avoid passive voice.

- Vary sentence length.
- Cut unnecessary words.
- Replace cliches with original phrasing.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The text provides a comprehensive overview of the importance of both reading and writing skills, highlighting their interconnectedness and the benefits of simultaneously teaching and practicing them. It emphasizes the significance of instructional techniques in enhancing reading comprehension and underscores the need for educators to possess strong foundations in teaching reading strategies.

The introduction outlines the components essential for proficient reading, including phonemic awareness, oral reading fluency, phonics, comprehension, and vocabulary. It also emphasizes the importance of reading skills in various aspects of life, such as clear written communication in professional settings.

Furthermore, the text provides a detailed methodology for improving reading skills, offering seven strategies ranging from summarizing and note-taking to setting reading goals and dedicating time to read regularly. It also emphasizes the importance of practice in honing writing skills and provides practical tips for grammar and spelling, revising, seeking feedback, and structuring written communication effectively.

Overall, the text effectively communicates the importance of literacy skills and provides actionable strategies for both improving reading comprehension and enhancing written communication abilities. It underscores the idea that proficiency in reading and writing is not only crucial for academic success but also for success in various personal and professional endeavors.

Use an outline.

A blank page can be intimidating even for the most seasoned writers. Give yourself something to work with by laying out the structure of your piece in advance. Leave placeholders for placeholders for an introduction several paragraphs that provide support for your thesis and a conclusion and then use your mind map to fill in the details.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the best way to improve reading and writing skills encompasses a multifaceted approach that involves consistent practice, diverse reading materials, targeted feedback, and a growth mindset. Reading widely exposes individuals to various writing styles, vocabulary, and perspectives, fostering a deeper understanding of language nuances. Concurrently, practicing writing regularly, whether through journaling, creative writing exercises, or academic assignments, hones writing proficiency and encourages experimentation with different forms and genres. Additionally, seeking constructive feedback from peers, mentors, or educators helps identify areas for improvement and encourages continuous learning. Embracing

challenges and persisting through setbacks with a growth mindset is crucial for sustained progress. Ultimately, the journey to enhancing reading and writing skills is not only about mastering the mechanics of language but also about cultivating a lifelong love for learning and expression.

References:

1. Berg, K., Buchmann, F., Dybiec, The interface between morphology and graphemics. In *Written Language and Literacy* (Vol. 17, (2014) pp. 282–307)
2. K., & Fuhrhop, N. Content courtesy of Springer Nature, terms of use apply. Rights reserved. 314 N. Fuhrhop Chomsky, C. Reading, writing, and phonology. (1970).
3. Oktamovna, T. S. (2023). The Different Ways in Which Tenses, Person and Number Are Formed and Used in English Grammar. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(10), 310-314.
4. Verbtabelle Plus Italienisch. Stuttgart: Pons. Fuhrhop, N. (2017).
5. Sobirjonovna, S. M., & Oktamovna, T. S. (2023). ACTIVITIES FOR BEGINNER, INTERMEDIATE AND ADVANCED LEVEL LEARNERS. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 21, 241-245.
6. PONS Grammatik kurz & bündig. Portugiesisch. Stuttgart: Ernst Klett. Lexique. www.lexique.org/3-4-2019. Meisenburg, T. (1996).
7. Romanische Schriftsysteme im Vergleich. Eine diachrone Studie. Tübingen: Narr. Meisenburg, T. (2014).
8. Temirova, M. (2024, February). THE CONCEPT OF " LINGUOCULTUROLOGY" AND " LINGUO-MENTALITY" IN THE FIELD OF LINGUISTICS. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 132-134).
9. Sobirjonovna, S. M. (2023). TYPES OF PRONOUNS IN ENGLISH. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 1039-1041.
10. Temirova, M., & Qodirova, M. (2021). LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF CHILDREN'S POETRY (BASED ON ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES). *MUNDARIJA | TABLE OF CONTENTS | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ*, 57.
11. Sobirjonova, M. S. (2024). INGLIZ TILINI BOSHLANGICH SINFLAR KESIMIDA OQITISHDA INNOVATSION METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH. *FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA JURNALI | JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION, CULTURE AND INNOVATION*, 3(4), 216-219.
12. Boboqulovna, A. D., Davronovna, M. M., & Muhammadiyevna, D. S. (2024, April). NON-LITERARY VOCABULARY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE.

In *Actual Problems in Higher Education in the Era of Globalization: International Scientific and Practical Conference* (Vol. 7, pp. 62-65).

13. Amanova, O., Murodova, S., & Bo’ronova, M. (2022). THE ROLE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(5), 927-930.

14. Davronovna, M. M., & Muhammadiyevna, D. S. (2024). THE PROBLEM OF STYLISTIC CLASSIFICATION OF VOCABULARY. *ILM-FAN TARAQQIYOTIDA ZAMONAVIY QARASHLAR: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR*, 14, 12-15.

15. KHIDIROVA, M. A., & TEMIROVA, M. A. K. (2019). TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF PROVERBS FORMED WITH PROFESSIONS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK. *Развитие и актуальные вопросы современной науки*, (6), 29-31.

16. Murodova, S. (2022). IMPORTANCE OF BODY LANGUAGE IN TEACHING ENGLISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 123-126.